

STUDIES IN FRIES MIGRATION. PART XIII. FRIES REARRANGEMENT OF ACYL ESTERS OF METHYL 2:6-DIHYDROXYBENZOATE (METHYL γ -RESORCYLATE) AND 3:5-DIHYDROXY-BENZOIC ACID (α -RESORCYLIC ACID)

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The Fries rearrangement of methyl 2:6-diacetoxy- as well as -dibenzoyloxy-benzoate yields methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-acetyl- and -3-benzoyl-benzoates and the corresponding keto-acids respectively, hydrolysis occurring during the course of the migration. No diketone has been isolated. 3:5-Diacetoxy benzoic acid does not isomerise under the conditions of the Fries reaction.

In continuation of the previous work on the Fries migration of phenolic esters of hydroxybenzoic acids and their methyl esters (Shah *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 235; 1952, 29, 351), the Fries rearrangement of methyl 2:6-diacetoxy- and -dibenzoyloxy-benzoate (I:R = COMe and COPh) has been investigated.

Methyl 2:6-diacetoxybenzoate (I:R = COMe) isomerised to methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate (II:R = R₁ = Me) on heating with aluminium chloride at 110°. On alkaline hydrolysis of this ester, the corresponding acid (II:R₁ = H; R = Me) was obtained, which on decarboxylation afforded resacetophenone, thus establishing the structures of both the keto-acid and the ester. The migration at higher temperatures, 150°-155°, furnished only the keto-acid (II:R = Me; R₁ = H), hydrolysis occurring during the course of the migration. Similarly, methyl 2:6-dibenzoyloxybenzoate (I:R = COPh) afforded methyl 2:6-dihydroxy-3-benzoylbenzoate (II:R = Ph; R₁ = Me) and the corresponding acid (II:R = Ph; R₁ = H), when the reaction was carried out at room temperature in nitrobenzene. Without solvent, however, only the keto-acid was obtained, identical with the acid obtained by the hydrolysis of the keto-ester (II:R = Ph; R₁ = Me). Its constitution was proved by decarboxylating it to 4-benzoylresorcinol.

It is noteworthy that though both the favourable β -positions of the resorcinol nucleus are vacant for two migrating acyl groups to occupy, only one of the two β -positions is occupied by one of the two migrating acyl groups, leading to the formation of a mono-ketone. No 3:5-diketone derivative has been obtained, even if the migration is carried out at higher temperatures, which only favour the hydrolysis of the ester group. Thus, methyl 2:6-diacetoxybenzoate differs from its isomer, methyl 2:4-diacetoxybenzoate, which on migration yields methyl 3:5-diacetyl-2:4-dihydroxybenzoate, one of the acetyl groups occupying the difficultly accessible

γ -position, as described in a previous communication (Shah *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). The Friedel-Crafts acetylation of methyl 2:6-dihydroxybenzoate (I:R = H) yields similar results (cf. Desai, Radha and Shah, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1945, **23A**, 305).

The Fries isomerisation of 3:5-diacetoxybenzoic acid (α -resorcylic acid) was attempted under various experimental conditions, but no ketonic product could be isolated, only the deacetylated acid having been recovered. The behaviour of this acid is analogous to that of *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid in this respect (Shah *et al.*, *loc. cit.* cf. Mauthner, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1933, *ii*, **136**, 205). The Friedel-Crafts acetylation of methyl α -resorcyate as well as of the free acid was also found to be unsuccessful (cf. Mody and Shah, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1951, **34A**, 77).

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 2:6-dihydroxybenzoate (I:R = H) was prepared from 2:6-dihydroxybenzoic acid (Kelkar and Limaye, this *Journal*, 1935, **12**, 783) by Fischer-Spier's method and crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 68-69°.

Methyl 2:6-diacetoxybenzoate (I:R = COMe) was prepared by sodium acetate-acetic anhydride method by heating the ester for 3 to 4 hours on a water-bath. It crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 73-74°. It does not develop any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and is insoluble in alkali. (Found: C, 57.0; H, 4.7. $C_{12}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent).

Fries Migration of (I:R = COMe): *Formation of Methyl 2:6-Dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoate* (II:R = R₁ = Me).—An intimate mixture of the ester (1 g.) and aluminium chloride (1.8 g.) was heated for an hour at 110°, HCl fumes evolving at about 65°. It was then treated with ice and HCl (5 c.c.). The solid obtained was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol in small needles, m.p. 136-37°. (Found: C, 57.0; H, 4.8. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8 per cent). The compound develops red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride and dissolves in alkali with yellow colour, but is insoluble in sodium bicarbonate. It is identical with the Friedel-Crafts acetylation product of Desai, Radha and Shah (*loc. cit.*).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared by the usual method, crystallised in needles from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 272-73° (decomp.). Desai, Radha and Shah report the same m. p.

Hydrolysis: Formation of 2:6-Dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoic Acid (II:R₁ = H; R = Me).—The keto-ester (II:R = R₁ = Me) (0.5 g.) was dissolved in NaOH (10 c.c., 10%) and the yellowish solution was left overnight at room temperature. It was then acidified and the solution extracted with ether; the brownish solid obtained after removal of the ether crystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 209-10° (decomp.). (Found: C, 54.9; H, 4.1. $C_9H_8O_5$ requires C, 55.1; H, 4.1 per cent). It develops a deep red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Methyl 2:6 diacetoxybenzoate (I:R = COMe) was isomerised at 150°-155° as before; on working up the reaction mixture, no solid product was obtained. It was therefore extracted with ether from which a brownish product was obtained and identified as 2:6-dihydroxy-3-acetylbenzoic acid (II:R₁ = H; R = Me) after crystallisation from hot water by mixed melting point with the sample obtained above.

Decarboxylation of the Acid (II:R, = H; R = Me).—The keto-acid (0.3 g.) was refluxed with water (20 c.c.) containing a few drops of HCl for 5 to 6 hours. On cooling, a solid separated which was collected and crystallised from hot water, m.p. 142-43°, identical with resacetophenone by mixed m.p. with an authentic sample.

Methyl 2:6-dibenzoyloxybenzoate (I:R = C₆H₅) was prepared by Schotten-Baumann method by quickly adding benzoyl chloride (4.5 g., 2.2 M) to the ice-cold solution of methyl 2:6-dihydroxybenzoate (2.5 g., 1 M) in NaOH (15 c.c., 15%). It was well shaken and kept cool; after half an hour, the smell of benzoyl chloride vanished completely. A pasty mass separated, which solidified on washing with cold water. It was then crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 88°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 70.5; H, 4.2. C₂₂H₁₆O₄ requires C, 70.2; H, 4.2 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali solution and does not respond to ferric chloride colour test.

Fries Migration of (I:R = C₆H₅): *Formation of Methyl 2:6-Dihydroxy-3-benzoylbenzoate* (II:R₁ = Me; R = Ph) and the corresponding Acid (II:R₁ = H; R = Ph).—(a). An intimate mixture of the benzoyloxy-ester (1.8 g., 1 M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.5 g., 3.3 M) was heated at 120°-130° in an oil-bath for 1 hour. HCl gas was copiously evolved at 100°. The solid, obtained on working up the reaction mixture as before, dissolved completely with effervescence in dilute sodium bicarbonate solution (5%), which on acidification afforded a pale yellow solid, crystallising from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles, m.p. 185° (efferv.), yield 0.8 g. (Found: Equiv., 256.8; C, 64.9; H, 3.8. C₁₄H₁₀O₅ requires equiv., 258; C, 65.1; H, 3.9 per cent).

(b). The above migration was repeated by keeping the reaction mixture of the benzoyloxy-ester (1.8 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.5 g.), dissolved in dry nitrobenzene (15 c.c.), at room temperature for 24 hours, with CaCl₂ guard-tube. The reaction mixture was then worked up as usual. After removal of the nitrobenzene by steam-distillation, the residual solid was extracted with dilute sodium hydroxide solution (5%) and the yellow alkaline filtrate on acidification afforded a solid, which on treatment with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) partly dissolved with effervescence. The bicarbonate-insoluble product crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow shining needles, m.p. 121°. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 4.5. C₁₅H₁₂O₅ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.4 per cent). The solid obtained on acidifying the bicarbonate filtrate was identified as the keto-acid (II:R₁ = H; R = Ph). Both the keto-ester and acid dissolve in alkali solution with a yellow colour and develop a red colour with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The *keto-ester* (II:R₁ = Me; R = Ph), obtained above, was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid (II:R₁ = H; R = Ph) by sodium hydroxide (10%), the acid being identified as 2:6-dihydroxy-3-benzoylbenzoic acid by mixed m.p.

Decarboxylation of the keto-acid (II:R₁ = H; R = Ph) (0.5 g.), by heating it with water (30 c.c.), acetic acid (2 c.c.) and a few drops of HCl (conc.) for 15-18 hours on a sand-bath furnished 4-benzoylresorcinol, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample, 144-45°.

3:5-Dihydroxybenzoic acid or α -resorcylic acid ("Org. Syn", 1941, vol. 21, p. 27), acetylated by acetic anhydride-pyridine method, afforded 3:5-diacetoxybenzoic acid, which was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 156-57°.

The Fries migration of the above diacetoxy compound was attempted under a variety of conditions but only the deacetylated product was recovered.

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